

FEMALE LEADERS' CHARACTERISTICS AND INSTRUCTIONAL STYLES: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

A leader's gender should not hinder effective leadership. However, studies indicate that women continue to be underrepresented in the field of leadership in education despite the presence of more women in the classroom. Several stereotypes about women being ineffective or not suitable for the role continue to hinder women's ascension to leadership. This systematic literature review analyzed twenty (20) research articles to identify female instructional leaders' characteristics and leadership styles. The review also determined the instructional practices of female leaders. Results revealed that women leaders are collaborative and empathetic, which helped them build positive relationships with teachers, stakeholders, and the community. Moreover, women leaders are more active instructional leaders because of the skills they acquire in long years of teaching before getting promoted. As revealed, three leadership styles are associated with women: transformational leadership, delegation leadership, and participative/democratic leadership, with the latter being the most notable.

Keywords: *Female leaders, attributes, instructional style, leadership styles, systematic review*

INTRODUCTION

Instructional Leadership is a core aspect of school leadership that prioritizes teaching and learning in school decision-making. It requires principals to focus on enhancing student learning (Shaked et al., 2018).

According to Spillane and Louis (2002), "Without an understanding of the knowledge necessary for teachers to teach well – content knowledge, general pedagogical knowledge, content-specific pedagogical knowledge, curricular knowledge, and knowledge of learners – school leaders will be unable to perform essential school improvement functions such as monitoring instruction and supporting teacher development. The "leadership content knowledge" necessary for instructional leadership was described as "that knowledge of subjects and how students teach them that is used by administrators when they function as instructional leaders" by Stein & Nelson (2003). Studies have shown a connection between the principals' instructional leadership and students' achievements (Glickman et al., 2014). Instructional leadership's effects on student outcomes were three to four times higher than that of transformational leadership, which sees leaders as inspiring, empowering, and motivational to followers (Robinson et al., 2008). Research has shown a small but statistically significant gender effect when comparing men and women in the context of instructional leadership, with female principals regularly receiving higher ratings on instructional leadership when compared with their male counterparts. (Hallinger, Li, and Wang 2016). Moreover, according to Carli & Eagly (2016), women often manifest transformational leadership more often than men.

The education sector is considered a 'woman's job' since classroom teaching manifests the same tasks expected of women: nurturing and caring for children, while men possess qualities that are more applicable to organizational leadership (Carli & Eagly, 2011; Fuller, 2017). Several countries have identified the underrepresentation of women in the school leadership roles (Bush, 2017; Shakeshaft, 1987), and one of the most significant barriers to women's rise to leadership is the difficulty of balancing a demanding school leadership role with family responsibilities that are continuously assumed by women (Arroyo, 2019; Bush, 2017; Fuller, 2017; Fuller, 2009). This is likely why women typically fill these roles with fewer family responsibilities, such as those who live alone or have grown children (Coleman, 2001, 2012). A female leaders need to establish her name and overcome the issues and challenges that come with their leadership. Stereotypes of male and female educational leaders show that males are better leaders because they are rational, decisive, and strong, while female leaders are emotional and too soft, negatively affecting their leadership style.

Research Questions

- 1.What are the Personal Characteristics and Professional Attributes of Female Educational Leaders?
- 2.What are the common leadership styles of women based on their characteristics?
- 3.How do female educational leaders practice instructional leadership?

METHODOLOGY

The systematic literature review is a method where all available research regarding a formulated question, topic, or area of interest is identified, selected, and evaluated to provide a clear understanding (Dewey et al., 2016). It is an efficient way to compile

different research and explore differences among the studies about a specific topic. A systematic review adheres to standardized methodologies and guidelines in systematic searching, filtering, reviewing, critiquing, interpreting, synthesizing, and reporting findings from multiple publications on a topic or domain of interest (Pati & Lorusso, 2017). Because a systematic review does not entail data acquisition for a new research topic and instead uses prior research, it is categorized as secondary research.

Moreover, a systematic literature review helps identify patterns and trends in research and gaps and contradictions in the literature. The literature review offers accurate and current summaries of the best available evidence, which can assist in informing practice, policy, and decision-making. Thus, this method is used in this study.

The first step to achieving the goals of this study is to find research articles and studies on the perceived characteristics and leadership styles of female instructional leaders in multiple databases such as Google Scholar, ERIC, and Research Gate, to name a few. The eligibility requirements set prior to the identification, location, and retrieval of the research required to address the issue of evidence-based practice served as the foundation for the search procedure.

Using the available databases with the following keywords: characteristics of female school principals, women leadership in education, women leadership styles, and attributes of female educational leaders; from the initial thirty (30) pieces of literature counted, twenty (20) papers matched the following initial inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria should cover at least one topic from characteristics of women educational leaders, women's leadership styles, or women's practice of instructional leadership. Additionally, the published articles should be peer reviewed with full papers available in databases. On the other hand, the excluded articles are published articles that need clear information on the characteristics of women educational leaders, women's leadership styles, and women's practice of instructional leadership. Articles with no full paper available in the database are also excluded. The timeframe for inclusion is from 2015 to 2024.

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Presence of at least one of the characteristics of women educational leaders, women's leadership styles, and women's practice of instructional leadership.	Absence of characteristics of women educational leaders, women's leadership styles, women's practice of instructional leadership.
Primary research published in peer-reviewed journals	Book reviews, editorials, and literary critiques
Full paper must be available in the database.	Only contain the title and abstract.
Published articles from 2015 to 2024.	Research articles or papers that have yet to be published from 2015 to 2024.

RESULTS

Table 2 below shows the research articles included in the systematic review along with the respective authors and publication date.

Table 2. Research Articles included in the systematic review of literature

Research No.	Author/s	Research Title	Year of Publication
1	Vogel, L. R., Alhudithi A., & Alsliman, A.	A Comparison of Male and Female Saudi School Principals' Perspectives of Instructional Leadership.	2021
2	Shaked, H., Gross, Z., & Glanz, J.	Between Venus and Mars: Sources of Gender Differences in Instructional Leadership	2017
3	Weinstein, J., Sembler, M., Weinstein, M., Marfán, J., Valenzuela, P., & Muñoz, G.	A female advantage? Gender and educational leadership practices in urban primary schools in Chile	2021
4	Shaked, H., Gross, Z., & Glanz, J.	Gender differences in instructional leadership: how male and female principals perform their instructional leadership role	2018
5	Ismail, A., Ahmad, N. S., & Aman, R. C.	Gender of transformational school principals and teachers' innovative behavior	2021
6	Isnaini, R. L., Arifin, Z., Rahmi, S., & Syafii, A	Gender-based leadership in quality assurance development: A phenomenological study.	2023
7	Dugas, K., & Cerna, M. G. D.	Investigating Attributes of Women Leaders: Exploratory Approach	2022
8	Mert, P.	Leadership characteristics of female school principals according to female teachers	2021
9	Vogel, L. R., & Alhudithi, A.	Arab women as instructional leaders of schools: Saudi and Qatari female principals'	2021

		preparation for and definition of instructional leadership	
10	Abdon, L., Farin, E., & Farin, A.	Emotional Intelligence, Leadership Qualities and Decision-Making Practices Of Female Administrators In Selected Secondary Schools In Region III, Philippines	2017
11	Özcan, K., Balyer, A., & Firat, F.	Factors Affecting Trust in Female And Male School Leaders	2022
12	Almedora, C., Niez, R., & Bentor, C. T.	Effectiveness of Principle-Centered Leadership And Characteristics of the School Heads in Leyte Division, Philippines	2016
13	Alberto, M. O.	Leadership of Woman President in the Philippine State Universities and Colleges	2023
14	Perez, E. L. A.	Philippine Women Educators' Leadership Styles and Managerial Skills	2021
15	Nicolas, W. J.	Leadership Style of Women Leaders in the Academe Industry: A Heuristic Analysis	2019
16	Entoma S. S.	Attributes of Women Leaders of State Colleges and Universities in Eastern Visayas, Philippines	2016
17	Mulawarman, W. G., & Komariyah, L	Women and Leadership Style in School Management: Study of Gender Perspective	2021
18	Howard Jr., D	Gender Leadership Styles in Higher Education: A Transformational Leadership Study	2023
19	Redmond, P., Gutke, H., Galligan, L., Howard, A., & Newman, T.	Becoming a female leader in higher education: investigations from a regional university. Gender and Education	2016

20	Read, B., & Kehm, B. M.	Women as leaders of higher education institutions: a 2016 British–German comparison
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1. Personal Characteristics and Professional Attributes of Female Instructional Leaders

Personal characteristics and professional attributes are the qualities or features that are distinct or common and make someone recognizable. Based on the literature, identified below are the personal characteristics and professional attributes of Female Instructional Leaders that influence their leadership style and instructional leadership practices.

Table 3. Personal Characteristics and Professional Attributes of Female Instructional Leaders

Personal Characteristics/ Professional Attributes	Research Article
<i>Building Relationships</i>	
1. Collaboration with teachers to improve practice	1, 2, 4, 11, 12, 13, 14,19
2. Building relationships with the community and other stakeholders	1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 11, 12, 13, 14, 20
3. Empathetic and Compassionate	2, 8, 11, 12, 13, 16,17
4. Ability to motivate their subordinates	6, 7, 13, 16,19
5. Openness	6, 7, 10, 12, 13,19,20
<i>Professional Expertise</i>	
1. Lifelong Learning	1
2. Hands-on	1, 7, 11, 14,17
3. Instructional Experts	2, 6, 9, 10, 13, 14,17
4. Supportive	2, 3, 7, 8,17
5. Sets clear time targets	6, 7, 16
6. Detailed, thorough, and meticulous	6, 7, 8, 11, 14
7. Initiative, Innovative, Problem-Solving Skills	7, 8, 9, 10, 13,17
<i>Values-Oriented</i>	
1. Model fairness and Equity	1, 11, 13,19
2. Passionate and Dedicated	7, 11, 12,17
3. Integrity, Honesty and Trustworthy	7, 11, 12, 16
4. Perseverance	5,7,17,19
5. Egoistic	7
6. Acting Emotionally	8, 11

2. Instructional Leadership Practices

Table 4. Instructional Leadership Practices

Instructional Leadership Practices	Research Article
1. Supervision of Teachers	
A. Classroom Observation/ Monitoring	1, 2, 3, 9, 14,17
B. Feedback to Teachers	1, 4, 9, 10,17
C. Supporting the Use of Technology in the Classroom / Technical Support	1, 3,17
D. Personal Review of Student Achievement Data	1, 12
2. Modeling of Lifelong Learning	1, 16,17,18
3. Support of New Teaching Strategies through Professional Development	1, 4, 9, 15,17
4. Development of Curriculum such as enrichment courses	1, 9,17
5. Obtaining needed resources and communicating with stakeholders	1, 4
6. Setting Direction (Vision, Objectives, Targets, and Deadlines)	3, 6,17

3. Leadership Styles of Female Instructional Leaders

Table 5. Common Leadership Styles of Female Instructional Leaders

Leadership Styles	Research Article
1. Transformational Leadership	1, 3, 4, 13,18
2. Delegative Leadership	5,14, 15
3. Participatory/Democratic/Facilitating Leadership	3, 4, 5,6, 13, 14, 15, 16,17,19,20

DISCUSSION

1. Personal Characteristics and Professional Attributes of Female Instructional Leaders

Personal characteristics and professional attributes are the qualities or features that are distinct or common and make someone recognizable. Based on the literature, identified

below are the personal characteristics and professional attributes of Female Instructional Leaders that influence their leadership style and instructional leadership practices.

The table 3 above shows female instructional leaders' different personal characteristics and professional attributes. The characteristics are grouped into three categories: building relationships, professional expertise, and values-oriented.

Building Relationships. Influential leaders are good at building relationships. The Female Instructional Leaders' characteristics identified in this literature related to building relationships include collaborating with teachers to improve practice, building relationships with the community and other stakeholders, being empathetic and compassionate, motivating, being cooperative and being open and flexible, and having excellent communication skills. Communicating with the teachers and stakeholders is an essential skill that an instructional leader must possess because they serve as partners in achieving the goals of improving the teaching and learning process (Garegae, 2007). As the saying goes, "It takes a village to educate a child," the literature emphasizes the female instructional leaders' ability to build relationships with the community and other stakeholders, with 11 out of 20 pieces of literature mentioning this characteristic. Female leaders' empathetic and compassionate communication may have contributed to better relationships not only with the stakeholders but also with the teachers. Female leaders are open to feedback, listen to their colleagues' opinions, and provide learning opportunities, encouraging teachers to express themselves.

Professional Expertise. Female leaders are considered instructional experts, having more teaching experience, training attended, and organizational experience than their male counterparts. Women were typically appointed as principals after gaining more years of teaching experience and completing more academic and professional studies than men (Grogan & Shakeshaft, 2010; Roser et al., 2009). Since they have more experience in the teaching and learning process, female leaders are more hands-on in teacher supervision and are detailed, meticulous, innovative, and efficient problem solvers.

Values-oriented. Female leaders commonly exhibit integrity and honesty and are trustworthy. Based on the findings of Özcan et al., (2022), teachers trust their female leaders more because of their dedicated behaviors and their motherly, sensitive, and compassionate personalities. They are meticulous and devoted to their work. Interestingly, only two articles mentioned acting emotionally as a female leader's characteristic, which contradicts the stereotype that female leaders are emotional and, therefore, unsuitable to lead.

2. Instructional Leadership Practices

Table 5 shows the different ways in which female instructional leaders practice instructional leadership. The themes are adopted and modified from the six themes of

instructional leadership that emerged from the results in Female Saudi School Principals' Perspectives of Instructional Leadership in article 1.

Supervision of Teachers. Consistent with the studies of Grogan & Shakeshaft (2010) and Roser et.al (2009), when compared with their male counterparts, the Female Israeli Principals' teaching experience prior to leadership is more extended (Shaked et al., 2017). In the same study, 61% of Female Principals considered themselves to have instructional proficiency, which enabled them to actively engage in instructional leadership, particularly in classroom observation and supervision. Because female instructional leaders have gained more years of experience as teachers, they are more familiar with the teaching and learning process; thus, the supervision of teachers is their primary task in instructional leadership.

Modeling of Lifelong Learning. Female Instructional Leaders consider modeling lifelong or continuous learning as one of their roles as instructional leaders. It can be through obtaining a postgraduate degree, additional training, consulting with experts or colleagues, or conducting research. Female instructional leaders consider updating one's knowledge and skills vital to being a successful instructional leader.

Support of New Teaching Strategies through Professional Development. By closely monitoring the teachers and students, female educational leaders know first-hand the needs of the teachers to improve their performance, which leads to the crafting of effective professional development for teachers. The delivery of professional development training will ultimately benefit the students since improving the teachers' skills will also help improve the students' development.

Development of Curriculum such as enrichment courses. While schools are mandated to abide by the national curriculum provided by the government, Female Instructional Leaders in Saudi Arabia and Qatar revealed that they added enrichment classes such as foreign language electives, and computer and physical education subjects. Enrichment options include establishing extracurricular activities such as clubs, community festivals, and non-curriculum activities such as field trips and school carnivals. This helped enrich the students' academic performance and social and emotional aspects and increased their engagement with the school.

They are obtaining needed resources and communicating with stakeholders. Instructional Leaders must perform traditional management duties such as budgeting, facilities maintenance, and the aforementioned instructional leadership practices related to teaching and learning (DiPaola & Hoy, 2008; Rigby, 2014). Female Instructional Leaders include obtaining needed resources as part of problem solving and communication with stakeholders as part of decision making. Since schools cannot operate on their own, stakeholders such as parents, LGUs, and private institutions work together to address the needs of the school, may it be the recruitment of effective teachers or goods and services to repair and maintain the school facilities (Vogel et al., 2021).

Setting Direction (Vision, Objectives, Targets and Deadlines). Based on the study by Isnaini in 2023, Chilean participants perceive Female Leaders as leaders who work with

clear time targets, which ensure the effective and efficient completion of tasks. Being led by a woman means having set daily targets, adherence to deadlines, and consistent follow-up meetings to oversee the preparation and implementation of programs. This is consistent with the study of Weinstein in 2021, where the average number of teachers who agree or strongly agree that their female principals set a clear direction in vision and objectives is higher than that of their male counterparts.

3. Leadership Styles of Female Instructional Leaders

Transformational Leadership. Transformational Leadership is increasingly linked with female leadership, which is increasingly valued in educational leadership (Thorpe, 2018). Female leaders tend to be associated more with communal traits such as problem-solving, the development and empowerment of followers, and responsiveness to followers' individual needs, which characterizes transformational leadership (Eagly & Karau, 2002). Female instructional leaders associated their perception of instructional leadership with maintaining positive relationships with teachers demonstrating transformational leadership. Transformational leaders inspire, empower, and encourage their followers. One of the studies cited that, as a female leader, she demands transformative changes and wants to leave a legacy of being open to change, being a leader by example, and nurturing future leaders.

Delegative Leadership. A leader who practices delegative leadership delegates the responsibilities to their subordinates and expects them to take ownership of the tasks. One of the studies showed that women leaders consider this leadership style very high as rated by themselves. The characteristics of Delegative Leadership included in the study are delegating broad responsibilities to staff and expecting them to handle the details; expecting staff to find and correct their errors; providing clear objectives and boundaries to team members; giving relevant and appropriate advice to subordinates; and devolves team management to the team itself. Sometimes it is called laissez-faire leadership, but there is a subtle difference in autonomy. Laissez-faire leadership employs an entirely hands-off approach, while delegating leadership is still involved but allows certain autonomy.

Participative/Democratic/Facilitating Leadership. Consistent with Eagly and her colleagues' (1992) meta-analysis, which found that female principals tend to adopt more participatory, democratic leadership styles, one of the studies' findings revealed that female principals linked instructional leadership to maintaining positive relationships with the school staff, which involves partnership, empowering others, and other forms of cooperation. In the study in Indonesia, the extensive networking ability of female university leaders was beneficial in creating personal connections with stakeholders, which is one of the critical aspects of leadership. Moreover, interviewees in the study perceived women leaders as more cooperative and flexible. They offer more spaces for participation and collaboration (Eagly & Carli, 2007). This is supported by Northouse's research (2013) findings, which found that female leaders demonstrate participatory leadership more frequently than their male counterparts. This leadership style is most notable in the study of women educational leaders in SUCs in the NCR where 57% of the respondents stated that they are more inclined to participative and democratic leadership

styles. One practice of this leadership style is that when a woman administrator prepares the plan for their assessment or planning sessions, she presents it to her subordinates and lets them critique it. From there, they develop an output showing that women leaders strongly involve others in the decision-making process. This practice was also mentioned in the study in Eastern Visayas' SUCs. According to Perez (2021), democratic leadership is the most appropriate in democratic nations like the Philippines. The desire for democracy in any aspect of leadership is embedded in the nation's history.

Conclusions

The literature review determined the characteristics, leadership styles, and practice of instructional leadership of women leaders. Women instructional leaders' personal characteristics and professional attributes were grouped into three categories: Building Relationships, Professional Expertise, and Values-Oriented. Women Leaders are known for their skills in building positive relationships with stakeholders and the community and initiating collaboration with teachers. They are open to the ideas of their colleagues, making them comfortable voicing their opinions and suggestions. Aside from this, women leaders are also considered instructional experts. Women tend to be recruited for leadership positions in later years after serving as teachers for a long time, resulting in their detailed, meticulous and hands-on instructional leadership. Women instructional leaders focus on supervising teachers and conducting professional development to address the needs of the teachers. Further, the research articles included in this study inclined women leaders more toward a participative or democratic leadership style. Gender should not be considered as a roadblock to good leadership. Instead, an individual's capacity for performance and leadership should be assessed in light of their accomplishments, skills, and abilities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare no conflict of interest, no bias and the research focus only on analyzing studies.

REFERENCES

- Arroyo, D. (2019). Women's leadership in education: A perspective from Chilean school leaders. MA Dissertation, University of Nottingham, UK.
- Bush, T. (2017). Gender and leadership in primary education. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 45(6), 903–906.
- Carli, L., & Eagly, A. (2011). Leadership and gender. In: Day D and Antonakis J (eds) *The Nature of Leadership*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, pp.437–476.
- Carli, L., & Eagly, A. (2016). Women face a labyrinth: An examination of metaphors for women leaders. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 31(8), 514-527. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GM-02-2015-0007>
- Coleman, M. (2001). Achievement against the odds: The female secondary headteachers in England and Wales. *School Leadership & Management*, 21(1), 75–100.

- Coleman, M. (2007). Gender and educational leadership in England: A comparison of secondary headteachers' views over time. *School Leadership and Management*, 27(4), 383–399.
- Dewey, A., & Drahota, A. (2016). Introduction to systematic reviews: Online learning module Cochrane Training. Cochrane Training.
<https://training.cochrane.org/interactivelearning/module-1-introduction-conducting-systematic-reviews>
- DiPaola, M. F., & Hoy, W. K. (2008). *Principals Improving Instruction: Supervision, Evaluation, and Professional Development*. Boston, MA: Pearson Education.
- Eagly, A., Karau, S. & Johnson, B. 1992. "Gender and Leadership Style among School Principals: A Meta-Analysis." *Educational Administration Quarterly* 28 (1): 76–102.
- Eagly, A., & Carli, L. (2007) *Through the Labyrinth. The Truth About how Women Become Leaders*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- Eagly, A., & Karau, S. (2002). Role congruity theory of prejudice toward female leaders. *Psychological Review*, 109(3), 573-598. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0033-295X.109.3.573>
- Fuller, K. (2009). Women secondary head teachers: Alive and well in Birmingham, at the beginning of the twenty-first. *Management in Education*, 23, 19–31.
- Fuller, K. (2017). Women secondary head teachers in England: Where are they now? *Management in Education*, 31(2), 54–68.
- Garegae, K. G. (2007). Closing the Missing Link in Ethnomathematics Research: The Socio-Affective Dimension of Cultural Artifacts. *AlterNative: An International Journal of Indigenous Peoples*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/117718010700300204>
- Glickman, C. D., Gordon, S. P., & Ross-Gordon, J. M. (2014). *Supervision and Instructional Leadership: A Developmental Approach* (9th ed.). London, UK: Pearson.
- Grogan, M., & Shakeshaft, C. (2010). *Women and Educational Leadership*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Hallinger, P., Li, D., & Wang, W. C. (2016). Gender differences in instructional leadership: A meta-analytic review of studies using the Principal Instructional Management Rating Scale. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 52(4), 567–601.
- Howard Jr., D. (2023). Gender leadership styles in higher education: A transformational leadership study. *Open Journal of Leadership*, 12, 543-561.
<https://doi.org/10.4236/ojl.2023.124024>
- Isnaini, R. L., Arifin, Z., Rahmi, S., & Syafii, A. (2023). Gender-based leadership in quality assurance development: A phenomenological study. *Cogent Education*, 10(2).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2023.2255078>
- Meta-Analytic Review of Studies Using the Principal Instructional Management Rating Scale. (n.d.). *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 50(4), 610–644.
- Northouse, P. G. (2013). *Leadership: Theory and Practice* (6th ed.). Sage Publications, Inc.
- Özcan, K., Balyer, A., & Fırat, F. (2022). Factors affecting trust in female and male school leaders. *International Journal of Educational Leadership and Management*.
<https://doi.org/10.17583/ijelm.9811>
- Pati, D., & Lorusso, L. N. (2017). How to write a systematic review of the literature. *HERD*, 11(1), 15–30. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1937586717747384>
- Perez, E. L. A. (2021). Philippine women educators' leadership styles and managerial skills. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 10(3), 438–455.
<https://european-science.com/eojnss/article/view/6258>
- Rigby, J. G. (2014). Three logics of instructional leadership. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 50(4), 610–644.
- Robinson, V. M. J., Lloyd, C., & Rowe, K. (2008). The impact of leadership on student outcomes: An analysis of the differential effects of leadership types. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 44(5), 564–588.

- Roser, V., Brown, M., & Kelsey, C. (2009). Principal gender as related to campus size, level and academic rating. *Advancing Women in Leadership Journal*, 29(10), 2–14.
- Shaked, H., Glanz, J., & Gross, Z. (2018). Gender differences in instructional leadership: How male and female principals perform their instructional leadership role. *School Leadership and Management*, 38(4), 417–434. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2018.1427569>
- Shaked, H., Gross, Z., & Glanz, J. (2017). Between Venus and Mars: Sources of gender differences in instructional leadership. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 47(2), 291–309. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143217728086>
- Shakeshaft C (1987) Women in Educational Administration. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Spillane, J. P., & Louis, K. S. (2002). School improvement process and practices: Professional learning for building instructional capacity. In J. Murphy (Ed.), *The Educational Leadership Challenge: Redefining Leadership for the 21st Century* (pp. 83–104). University of Chicago: Chicago, IL.
- Stein, M. K., & Nelson, B. S. (2003). Leadership content knowledge. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 25(4), 423–448.
- Thorpe, A. (2018). Educational leadership development and women: Insights from critical realism. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 22(2), 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2018.1450995>
- Vogel, L. R., Alhudithi, A., & Alsliman, A. (2021). A comparison of male and female Saudi school principals' perspectives of instructional leadership. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 4(1), 67-81. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eujem.4.1.67>
- Weinstein, J., Sembler, M., Weinstein, M., Marfán, J., Valenzuela, P., & Muñoz, G. (2021). A female advantage? Gender and educational leadership practices in urban primary schools in Chile. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 51(5), 1105–1122. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17411432211019407>